

Investigating the Impact of Celebrity Endorsements on Consumer Brand Perception: An Analysis of the Mediating Role of Customer Attitude Toward the Brand on Purchase Intention with a Sustainability and Transformation Perspective in Pakistan's Pharmaceutical and Nutraceutical Industry

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Abstract

The current research study was Investigating the Impact of Celebrity Endorsements on Consumer Brand Perception: Analysis the Mediating role of Customer's Attitude toward Brand towards Consumer Purchase Intention perspective with the Industry of Pharmaceutical and Nutraceutical in Pakistan. The data collection with the help of the respondent, have the greater knowledge regarding the industry of the pharmaceutical and knowing the brands preferences in the city of Karachi. The technique of the sampling to be used, the non-probability, convenience sampling in the current research study. The results indicate the independent variables, Celebrity Trustworthiness, Celebrity Expertise, Celebrity Attractiveness, Celebrity Similarity, Celebrity Match-up Congruence positively and the significantly associated with the customer attitude towards brands. Further mediating effects, the customer's attitude towards brand mediates the relationship with the trustworthiness, celebrity expertise, celebrity attractiveness, celebrity similarity and the celebrity match-up congruence with the consumer purchase intention. Further results indicates that the customer's attitude towards positive impact on the customer purchase intention. The managerial implication of the research study to developed strategic planning and the strategies to increase firm productivity.

INTRODUCTION

Overview of the Research Study

The current research study was to examine the impact of the celebrity endorsement on the brand perception, with the mediating effects of the brand equity in the pharmaceutical industries of Pakistan. In the era of information technology, multinational companies through celebrity endorsement better understanding of the consumer behavior and due to this understanding increase the consumer purchase decisions based on online shopping, on time delivery, information access, time saving and easy of payment systems in the industry of pharmaceutical (Sanusi, 2020). Thus, these important factors more sustainability and the transformation of the consumer brand buying behavior in the industry of industry of Pharmaceutical & Nutraceutical (Ali, Nasir, & Haider, 2025). So that, better approach of celebrity endorsement will create the significance impact on the consumer purchase intentions and developed good relations with consumers and positive impact on the company image and strength (Shaw et al., 2022). Thus, through this approach the consumers create good relationships with companies and better understanding of the management strength, company credibility, company reliability, company responsibility, and the trustworthiness (Wang, 2023). The consumer can create the text messages, creates the images, audio functionality, video sharing through the technique of social media and the social media is one of the important factors of celebrity endorsement incorporates to sharing information to increase sale in the industry of Pharmaceutical & Nutraceutical (Annissa, & Paramita, 2021). The prior research study suggested that the celebrity endorsement significance and vital role consumer purchase behavior and to increase consumer purchase intention with developed

marketing strategic strategies using the celebrity endorsements and impact on consumer purchase intention (Ali, Khan, Iqbal, Bukhari, & Boumal, 2025). The current research study was used the approach of mixed methods and with the help of quantitative data analysis through questionnaire and with qualitative data through interview regarding the celebrity endorsement on consumer behavior with mediating effects of consumer attitude and the approach celebrity endorsement to comprehensive understanding of the consumer perceptions (Qiu et al., 2021). The selling of the goods and services through digitally in the field of marketing, the term digital technologies such as e-mail marketing, phone marketing, mobile marketing, display marketing to attractions to consumer and to increase consumer purchase intention (Ali et al., 2025). Because marketing is the most vital and significance impact on consumer behavior and marketing creates consumer values and integrates with advertising tools, society (Ikhwan, 2023). The research study explains that, the findings of the research study, the social media marketing have positive impact on consumer purchase behavior with consumer engagement mediating effects on consumer purchase intention (Shien et al., 2023). The social network marketing is the component of social media marketing and is the vital role on the consumer behavior. So that, this innovative marketing concept consumers and associated with brands without any limitations, no any time constraints, without any location (Oliveros-Coello, 2022). The prior study was suggested that the environmental sustainability associated with the consumer behavior and also the new inventions of internet tool, in the county of Pakistan, peoples easily access and sharing information, and provides strong support of the consumers

of the Pharmaceutical & Nutraceutical brands in Pakistan (Ali, Iqbal, Boumal, & Raza, 2025). Thus, with the help of internet, most of the companies sharing information regarding products, services, and increase the productivity of the marketing approach to increase consumer purchase intention. Many companies use the approach of celebrity endorsement, such as the social media, email marketing to increase consumer purchase intention. Because the consumers of the brands of Pharmaceutical & Nutraceutical received consent information regarding products through email marketing and consumers strongly engaged through social media factors and enhanced consumer purchase intention. In the prior research study suggested that the people interactions and online communications in the certain media platforms to be known as social media and whereas the email marketing is the way to communication targets audience through electronic mail to better delivered information to specific group of peoples (Koirala, 2023)

Background of the Research Study

Thus, in the industry of Pharmaceutical & Nutraceutical the approach of celebrity endorsement, and social media marketing also, digital selling is the marketing of goods and services with the help of digital technologies such as mobile marketing, internet, web site, display marketing and email marketing, mobile marketing to increase consumer purchase intention (Sohn, 2023). Actually, the approach of celebrity endorsement and the, social media, digital marketing is related to a sort of marketing which includes products through digital networks and increase purchase intention and reaching out to customers' needs and increasing customer satisfaction (Azgan Pektas & Hassan, 2020). In the prior research study suggested that celebrity endorsement

concept in the marketing one of the important factors in any services, business and to objective to create customer values with competitive advantage and organizational growth (Eren, 2020). Because now society integrated and becomes global village to gain benefits of the advertising and marketing approaches and customer interlink with digitally and as well as socially (Mehmood, Ali, & Shah, 2025). In the past research study explains that the expenditure of marketing, advertising budget more expensive before the utilization of digital marketing and also social media and production income level was low, and increasingly in term of cost effective and fast connectivity level increase (Kumar, 2020). In the celebrity endorsement, as the digital era, the new technologies components such as Facebook, twitter, Instagram are related to social media marketing and provides virtual platforms such as search engines, vlogs, microblogs, webpages integrated with digital channels in forms of new digital to increase brand awareness and brand perception (Adeola et al., 2022). Actually, customers are happier when using online shopping, and customers are considered as digital marketing for the purpose of fast connectivity and shopping in term of low cost and easy to access as compare to traditional marketing (Ali & Ahmed, 2023). So that the digital marketing, associated with the celebrity endorsement has greater opportunities in the Pharmaceutical & Nutraceutical and businesses in the future (Priya, 2023).

Problem Statement of the Research Study

In the Pakistan, Pharmaceutical & Nutraceutical, through the celebrity endorsement have faces diversification marketing strategies, with highly competitive environments, so that multinational companies need to developed effective

marketing strategies to increase consumer purchase intention. Therefore, the concept of celebrity endorsement rapid growth the consumer to attract potential customers and more relay on online marketing channels to fulfill the needs of the consumers. So that, needs to effectiveness celebrity endorsement in the marketing strategies which influencing on consumer behavior. Therefore, the current research study was examining the Impact of Celebrity Endorsements on Consumer Brand Perception: Analysis the Mediating role of Brand Equity in the industry of Pharmaceutical & Nutraceutical, Industry of Pakistan. Actually, the consumer behavior and consumer intentions impact on consumer attitude and the consumer attitude is based on the consumer trust, consumer beliefs and evaluation of products and consumer emotions towards brands, all these factors have significant impact on consumer behavior. In the prior research study suggested that consumer have various factors in the context of celebrity endorsement, such as consumer online experience, consumer experiences, the consumer mediating effects of attitude and consumer behavior have vital and significance role (Ali, Nasir, & Haider, 2025). Further the concept of celebrity endorsements has positive impact on consumer purchase intention because celebrities always play an important promotional tool for product, or brands to increase consumer purchase intention.

Research Objectives of the Research Study

The objective of the current research study was to examines the Impact of Celebrity Endorsements on Consumer Brand Perception: Analysis the Mediating role of Brand Equity in the industry of Pharmaceutical & Nutraceutical

RO1: To investigates the effects of celebrity endorsements on the behavior of consumer

and to increase purchase intention in the context of Pakistan.

RO2: To examines the mediating effects of brand equity with the association celebrity endorsements and consumer brand perceptions behavior.

RO3: To explore the explore the concept of celebrity endorsement with the relationship the consumer brand perceptions in the industry of Pharmaceutical & Nutraceutical, Pakistan.

Research Questions of the Research Study

Therefore, to attain the research study objectives, the following research questions will be focus during research study:

RQ-1) How influence the concept of celebrity endorsement on the behavior of consumer brand perception?

RQ-2) How does the mediating effects of brand equity on consumer brand perceptions in the industry of Pharmaceutical & Nutraceutical, Pakistan

RQ-3) What are the effects of celebrity endorsement on the behavior of consumer to increase consumer purchase intention?

Significance of the Research Study

The current research study has the both concepts of theoretical as well as practical significance in the industry of Pharmaceutical & Nutraceutical, Pakistan Therefore, the current research study includes the literature of consumer brand perceptions, marketing, consumer attitude and celebrity endorsement regarding the context of Pakistan, Pharmaceutical & Nutraceutical. Thus, research study examines the interconnected with digital marketing, consumer attitude, and Investigating the Impact of Celebrity Endorsements on Consumer Brand Perception and Analysis the Mediating role of Brand Equity in the industry of Pharmaceutical & Nutraceutical, to knowing the consumer brand

perceptions, consumer buying behavior and understanding decision making in the digital technologies, social media, environments and consumer purchase intention. With relate to the practically of the current research study, the results indicate could be significance importance in the industry of Pharmaceutical & Nutraceutical which operational activities in Pakistan. So that the better understanding the concept of celebrity endorsement with relate to consumer attitude and consumer purchase behavior to developed significance marketing strategies and resources allocations optimization. Further, better understanding of the role of celebrity endorsement as the moderating effect of brand equity on consumer behavior and companies increases the use of celebrity endorsement in marketing campaigns in Pakistan

Scope of the Research Study

The current research study closed to the industry of Pharmaceutical & Nutraceutical in Pakistan and main objective was to examines the impact of Celebrity Endorsements on Consumer Brand Perception: Analysis the Mediating role of Brand Equity in the industry of Pharmaceutical & Nutraceutical, to better understanding of the brand perceptions of the consumers. Therefore, the research study collects the data from the respondents have knowledge regarding the celebrities in the industry of Pharmaceutical & Nutraceutical brands in Pakistan. The current research study was to exploring the concept of celebrity endorsement with the behavior of consumer regarding the brand perceptions, and finds or identities the approach of celebrity endorsement with mediating effects of brand equity to with the behavior of consumer. Thus, the objective of the current research study examines the association of the celebrity endorsement with brand perceptions of the consumer behavior,

with the help of primary research approach to collect data questionnaires and also to collect information through interviews with relate to the topic of celebrity endorsement and the mediating effects of brand equity in the relationship consumer purchase intention in the industry of Pharmaceutical & Nutraceutical, Pakistan.

Celebrity Endorsement as a Marketing Strategy

The research study explained that for the purpose of promotions of products or brands celebrity endorsement significance importance and widely used in developing marketing strategies and consumer brand perception. The prior research study suggested that the celebrities have positive impact on consumer brand perception and through this approach creates the positive image on consumer behavior and build positive associations brand awareness, brand association, brand recall and developed consumer trust and loyalty (Goyal, 2012). In the industry of Pharmaceutical & Nutraceutical, used the celebrity endorsements for the purpose build emotional links and connections So that, through this approach to creates brand credibility, create differentiate products and trustworthiness of the celebrity to compete with competitors (Ahmed & Abedin, 2022).

Celebrity Endorsement and Physical Attractiveness

In the prior research study, explained the concept of celebrity endorsement and the physical attractiveness has the significance importance on the consumer perception of the brands. Because of physical attractiveness is the important component of the celebrity endorsement to expand the brands and more engaged the customers to increase the consumer (Sanusi, 2020). The prior research

study suggested that attitude of the behavior vital role in the association of the celebrity endorsement and the consumer buying behavior. Because of strategies of the celebrity endorsement, the personalization, contents writing, interactive images, change the attitude of the consumer towards products and developed positive image against the products (Ikhwan, 2023). So that better understanding of the behavior of consumers, and better understanding of the influences of celebrity endorsement towards attitude of the consumers. Therefore, the companies of the Pharmaceutical & Nutraceutical, developed significance marketing strategies, campaigns of marketing, promotional marketing strategies for the purpose of consumer buying behaviors, these factors effects on the consumer behaviors (Lee et al., 2020).

The Celebrity Endorsement and Celebrity/brand Congruency

The past research study was suggested that the in the field of marketing, the experts of the marketing incorporate the factor of the celebrity endorsements or takes the significance constructs, and increase the consumer beliefs to see the advertisements, and significance associations with the brand associations and brand perceptions (Lee et al., 2020). In the study of the celebrity endorsement, and developed the consumer brand perceptions, the advertisers focus on the significance and the best celebrity to developed and design the advertised, because of the consumer perceptions base on the believability of the celebrity and creates the positive impact on the consumer brand perception and brand association, brand image (Malik et al., 2023). Thus, the past research study explained that the role of moderating of the construct of celebrity endorsement has the effects on the association of the marketing of digital and the behavior of consumer (Ali et

al., 2023). Because of the factor of celebrity endorsement has the significance effects on the behavior of consumer and the digital marketing, will creates the brand credibility, brand trust, brand quality and brand availability, positive effects on consumer (Annisia, & Paramita, 2021). Due to the celebrity endorsement, the consumer perceived authenticity regarding brands, which creates the relationship of the celebrity endorsement as moderating, the digital marketing and the behavior of consumers. (Hussain, 2020). The prior research study was suggested that the in the past social psychology research the credibility and the beauty considered significance importance for delivered effective messages and these factors always important to increase consumer purchase intention. Thus, through the celebrity endorser transfer the cultural meaning of the products and creates effective endorsements (Yang et al., 2023).

Source Credibility and Consumer Brand Perception

The study was suggested that the high source of credibility positive impact on the perception of the consumer, regarding the brand image, brand recognition, and brand association. Actually, the credibility is associated with the believability and the further, results indicate the knowledge, expertise, and the trustworthiness which based on the credibility source or associated the word of mouth, which are the significance impact on the consumer brand perception (Fernandes et al., 2023)

Conceptual Research Model

In the current research study, the conceptual research model, developed incorporated, the independent variables, such as the celebrity physical attractiveness, the source credibility, and the celebrity/brand congruency, in the

model as independent variables, with the dependent variable consumer brand perception in the industry of Pharmaceutical & Nutraceutical

Figure: 2.1: Conceptual Research Model, Impact of celebrity endorsement with

Research Development Hypotheses

H1: Celebrity Trustworthiness has the significantly and the positively with the Customer's Attitude toward Brand

H2: Celebrity Expertise has the significantly and the positively with the Customer's Attitude toward Brand

H3: Celebrity Attractiveness has the significantly and the positively with the Customer's Attitude toward Brand

H4: Celebrity Similarity has the significantly and the positively with the Customer's Attitude toward Brand

H5: Celebrity Match-up Congruence with The Brand / Product has the significantly and the positively with the Customer's Attitude toward Brand

H6: Customer's Attitude toward Brand mediates the relationship with the Celebrity Trustworthiness and the Consumer Purchase Intention

H7: Customer's Attitude toward Brand mediates the relationship with the Celebrity Expertise and the Consumer Purchase Intention

H8: Customer's Attitude toward Brand mediates the relationship with the Celebrity Attractiveness and the Consumer Purchase Intention

H9: Customer's Attitude toward Brand mediates the relationship with the Celebrity Similarity and the Consumer Purchase Intention

H10: Customer's Attitude toward Brand mediates the relationship with the Celebrity Match-up Congruence and the Consumer Purchase Intention

H11: Customer's Attitude toward Brand has the significantly and the positively associated with the Consumer Purchase Intention

Research Design

The current research study based on the approach of quantity research technique to investigates the consumer attitudes as the effects of the celebrity endorsement as the associations behavior of consumer's brand perceptions, the industries of the Pharmaceutical & Nutraceutical in the Pakistan, Karachi. As the research is the way of collection of data, analysis the data, interpretation of data in form of systematic and as well as scientific way to solving the research problem and gives managerial implications. Whereas the methodology of research or research methodology is the approach of theoretical analysis in term of

systematic way of the research technique to be used in the research study. Thus, the research methodology includes the components such as research design, target audience or population, size of the sample to use in the research study, sampling technique to collect the data, data collection instruments, analysis of data, interpretation of data and implications of results of the research study (Kothari, 2014).

Research Onion

The important part in the research methodology, developing the research methodology considered as important steps or stages, which defines by Saunders' onion layers. Actually, the research onion better effective decision during the developing research methodology in the research study. The five important elements or research philosophy of the Saunders' research Onion are research philosophy, research approach, research strategy, time horizon and collection of data, gives better way of developing the research strategy (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2007). The current research study the positivism research philosophy includes in the study, because the concept of positivism is related to quantifiable research observation which is closed to analysis of the statistically and interpretations. The quantitative research approach which is based on the hypotheses testing and the data collection through questionnaire during the research study, which are related to positivism, thus when research based on the philosophy of positivism, more closed to structured way to explain the research study.

Sampling Technique and Data Collection Technique

The current research study was taken to collect the data through the questionnaire design, and questionnaire is based on the

systematic series of questions to asked the respondents Pharmaceutical & Nutraceutical the includes the methods of google forms and as well as physical questionnaire to distribute the questionnaire to respondents in the different retail super stores to collect the data, the help of the convenience sampling technique.

Data Analysis

With the help of Smart PLS 4.0 Software, to be analysis the data, is the good data analysis statistical technique.

Research Instruments Development

The research study includes the factors of the celebrity endorsement with the consumer purchase intention. The data collection through physical distributed questionnaire in the different hospitals and medical stores in the city of Karachi, and with the help google forms to sends questionnaire to fill the questionnaire forms and collect data with five-point Likert scale from 1 to 5.

Confirmatory factor analysis and scale validity

	C	Cr	C	A
onstructs	onbach's	omposite	omposite	verage
	alpha	Reliabili	Reliabili	Varianc
		ty	ty	e
				Extract
				ed
A	C	0.8	0.	0
	56	863	.636	
ATB	C	0.8	0.	0
	54	856	.632	
E	C	0.8	0.	0
	81	887	.677	
MC	C	0.8	0.	0
	54	856	.632	
PI	C	0.8	0.	0
	62	864	.648	
	C	0.8	0.	0

S	24	838	.584	
C	0.7	0.	0	
T	98	802	.554	

Based on the results, the values of the Cronbach's alpha, suggested that the research study factors, have values greater than 0.7, which means that all the constructs showing that reliability and the validity. Such as the reliability is based on internal consistency, since the results indicate that the Consumer Attitude (CA) value: 0.856, which is more than 0.7, thus the Consumer Attitude (CA) to fulfilled the criteria of reliability Such as the reliability is based on internal consistency, since the results indicate that the Consumer Attitude Toward Brand (CATB) value: 0.854, which is more than 0.7, thus the Consumer Attitude Toward Brand (CATB) to fulfilled the criteria of reliability. Such as the reliability is based on internal consistency, since the results indicate that the Celebrity Expertise (CE) value: 0.881, which is more than 0.7, thus the Celebrity Expertise (CE) to fulfilled the criteria of reliability Such as the reliability is based on internal consistency, since the results indicate that the Celebrity Match-up Congruence (CMC) value: 0.854, which is more than 0.7, thus the Celebrity Match-up Congruence (CMC) to fulfilled the criteria of reliability. Such as the reliability is based on internal consistency, since the results indicate that the Consumer Purchase Intention (CPI) value: 0.862, which is more than 0.7, thus the Consumer Purchase Intention (CPI) to fulfilled the criteria of reliability Such as the reliability is based on internal consistency, since the results indicate that the Celebrity Similarity (CS) value: 0.824, which is more than 0.7, thus the Celebrity Match-up Congruence to fulfilled the criteria of reliability Such as the reliability is based on internal consistency, since the results indicate that the Celebrity

Trustworthiness (CT) value: 0.798, which is more than 0.7, thus the Celebrity Trustworthiness (CT) to fulfilled the criteria of reliability

Average Variance Extracted

Through the values at the AVE, which is explained the convergent validity less than 0.5, all constructs are fulfilled the criteria of convergent validity, so that the current research study has the significant results with the criteria of convergent validity.

Path coefficient Model

Results Path Coefficients

Hypotheses	Relati onship s	P- Va lue s	Conc lusio n
			Supp orted
	CT ->	0.0	
	CATB	00	

H1: Celebrity Trustworthiness has the significantly and the positively With the Customer's

Attitude toward Brand			
H2: Celebrity Expertise has the significantly and the positively With the Customer's Attitude toward Brand	CE ->	0.000	Supported
H3: Celebrity Attractiveness has the significantly and the positively With the Customer's Attitude toward Brand	CA ->	0.029	Supported
H4: Celebrity Similarity has the significantly and the positively With the Customer's Attitude toward Brand	CS ->	0.000	Supported
H5: Celebrity Match-up Congruence with The Brand / Product has the significantly and the positively With the Customer's Attitude toward Brand	CMC ->	0.000	Supported
H11: Customer's Attitude toward Brand has the significantly and the positively associated With the Consumer Purchase Intention	CATB ->	0.000	Supported

The results showing that, the **H1:** Celebrity Trustworthiness has the significantly and the positively with the Customer's Attitude toward Brand, accepted, because of the probability values less than 0.05. thus, the hypothesis supported. **H2:** Celebrity Expertise has the significantly and the positively With the Customer's Attitude toward Brand, **H3:** Celebrity Attractiveness has the significantly

and the positively With the Customer's Attitude toward Brand,

H4: Celebrity Similarity has the significantly and the positively With the Customer's Attitude toward Brand,

H5: Celebrity Match-up Congruence with The Brand / Product has the significantly and the positively With the Customer's Attitude toward Brand and the

H11: Customer's Attitude toward Brand has the significantly and the positively associated With the Consumer Purchase Intention, thus, based on the results all the hypotheses supported.

Since the P-value = 0.000, which is less than 0.05, than conclude that the hypothesis

H1: Celebrity Trustworthiness (CT) is supported, thus the Celebrity Trustworthiness (CT) has important factor for Consumer Attitude Toward Brand (CATB).

Since the P-value = 0.000, which is less than 0.05, than conclude that the hypothesis

H2: Celebrity Expertise (CE) is supported, thus the Celebrity Expertise (CE) has important factor for Consumer Attitude Toward Brand (CATB).

Since the P-value = 0.029, which is less than 0.05, than conclude that the hypothesis

H3: Celebrity Attractiveness (CA) is supported, thus the Celebrity Attractiveness (CA) has important factor for Consumer Attitude Toward Brand (CATB).

Since the P-value = 0.000, which is less than 0.05, than conclude that the hypothesis

H4: Celebrity Similarity (CS) is supported, thus the Celebrity Similarity (CS) has important factor for Consumer Attitude Toward Brand (CATB).

Since the P-value = 0.000, which is less than 0.05, than conclude that the hypothesis

H5: Celebrity Match-up Congruence (CMC) is supported, thus the Celebrity Match-up Congruence (CMC) has important factor for Consumer Attitude Toward Brand (CATB).

Since the P-value = 0.000, which is less than 0.05, than conclude that the hypothesis

H11: Consumer Attitude Toward Brand (CATB) is supported, thus the Consumer Attitude Toward Brand (CATB) has important factor for Consumer Purchase Intention (CPI).

Analysis of Mediating Effects

Hypotheses	Relationsh ips	P- Valu es	Conclusi on
H6: Customer's Attitude toward Brand mediates the relationship with the Celebrity Trustworthi ness and the Consumer Purchase Intention	CT CATB CPI	-> -> .000	S upported
H7: Customer's Attitude toward Brand mediates the relationship with the Celebrity Expertise and the Consumer Purchase Intention	CE CATB CPI	-> -> .000	S upported
	CA	-> .000	S upported

H8: Customer's Attitude toward Brand mediates the relationship with the Celebrity Attractivene ss and the Consumer Purchase Intention	CATB CPI	->	
H9: Customer's Attitude toward Brand mediates the relationship with the Celebrity Similarity and the Consumer Purchase Intention	CS CATB CPI	-> -> .000	S upported
H10: Customer's Attitude toward Brand mediates the relationship with the Celebrity Match-up Congruence and the Consumer Purchase Intention	CMC CATB CPI	-> -> .000	S upported

Further results suggested that the

H6: Customer's Attitude toward Brand mediates the relationship with the Celebrity Trustworthiness and the Consumer Purchase Intention, **H7:** Customer's Attitude toward Brand mediates the relationship with the Celebrity Expertise and the Consumer Purchase Intention,

H8: Customer's Attitude toward Brand mediates the relationship with the Celebrity Attractiveness and the Consumer Purchase Intention,

H9: Customer's Attitude toward Brand mediates the relationship with the Celebrity Similarity and the Consumer Purchase Intention and

H10: Customer's Attitude toward Brand mediates the relationship with the Celebrity Match-up Congruence and the Consumer Purchase Intention, thus, based on the results indicates that all the hypotheses supported, Since the result, indicates that the P-value = 0.000, which is less than 0.05, than conclude that the hypothesis

H6: Celebrity Trustworthiness (CT) is supported, thus the Celebrity Trustworthiness (CT) has important factor for Consumer Attitude Toward Brand (CATB) and Consumer Purchase Intention (CPI). Since the result, indicates that the P-value = 0.000, which is less than 0.05, than conclude that the hypothesis

H7: Celebrity Expertise (CE) is supported, thus the Celebrity Expertise (CE) has important factor for Consumer Attitude Toward Brand (CATB) and Consumer Purchase Intention (CPI). Since the result, indicates that the P-value = 0.029, which is less than 0.05, than conclude that the hypothesis

H8: Celebrity Attractiveness (CA) is supported, thus the Celebrity Attractiveness (CA) has important factor for Consumer Attitude Toward Brand (CATB) Consumer

Purchase Intention (CPI). Since the result, indicates that the P-value = 0.000, which is less than 0.05, than conclude that the hypothesis

H9: Celebrity Similarity (CS) is supported, thus the Celebrity Similarity (CS) has important factor for Consumer Attitude Toward Brand (CATB) Consumer Purchase Intention (CPI). Since the result, indicates that the P-value = 0.000, which is less than 0.05, than conclude that the hypothesis

H10: Celebrity Match-up Congruence (CMC) is supported, thus the Celebrity Match-up Congruence (CMC) has important factor for Consumer Attitude Toward Brand (CATB) Consumer Purchase Intention (CPI).

Conclusion

The conclusion of the research study showing that the Celebrity Trustworthiness, Celebrity Expertise, Celebrity Attractiveness Celebrity Similarity and the Celebrity Match-up Congruence with The Brand / Product has the significantly and the positively With the Customer's Attitude toward Brand and Customer's Attitude toward Brand has the significantly and the positively associated With the Consumer Purchase Intention. The mediating effects of the Customer's Attitude toward Brand mediates the relationship with the Celebrity Trustworthiness and the Consumer Purchase Intention, and the Customer's Attitude toward Brand mediates the relationship with the Celebrity Expertise and the Consumer Purchase Intention, also Customer's Attitude toward Brand mediates the relationship with the Celebrity Attractiveness and the Consumer Purchase Intention and the Customer's Attitude toward Brand mediates the relationship with the Celebrity Similarity and the Consumer Purchase Intention and also Customer's Attitude toward Brand mediates the relationship with the Celebrity Match-up

Congruence and the Consumer Purchase Intention.

Theoretical Contribution

The current research study includes the literature of the body, based on the impact of the celebrity endorsements associated with the consumer brand attitudes on the consumer purchase intention. Thus, the developed the theoretical model and established the celebrity endorsements theory in the research study, the research hypotheses testing based on the data collected from the market of the Pakistan. Thus, the current research study contributes the empirical the developed the scales to investigated and measured the consumer brand attitudes and the consumer purchase intention and validate the results and the factors of the celebrity endorsement. Thus, the measured the developed the scales of the celebrity endorsements literature, with related to the cross-cultural consumer brand attitudes and the consumer purchase intention.

Practical Contributions

The contributions regarding the practically, the results of the current research study has the significance importance for the industry and the for the pharmaceutical policy makers and experts to developed the marketing strategies and strategic planning to examines the consumer brand attitudes and the consumer purchase intention.

Limitations and Further Research

The current research study, has several or some limitations regarding the budget, time limitation, limited resources. The current research study to collect the information or data in the city of Karachi
Later on, this study could be conducted in further cities, regions, and countries. The research model of the study was based on five

independent variables with one mediating variable and One dependent variable, further the research study could be included more independent and dependent variables with mediating and moderating variables to enhance the signification of this research study.

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